

A Study on Products and Services of ADOBE Inc.

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ABSTRACT

Adobe is an American Multinational Computer Software Company founded in December 1982 and founder of Adobe is John Warnock and Charles Geschke. Adobe has historically focused upon the creation of multimedia and creativity software product, with more recent foray toward rich internet application software development. It is best known for Photoshop, an image editing software Acrobat reader, the portable document format and Adobe Creative Cloud. Adobe headquartered at California, United States. As of 2018 Adobe has 19,560 employees worldwide about 40% of whom works in San Jose. The company offers a line of product and services used by professionals, marketers, knowledge worker application developers, enterprise and consumer for creating managing, delivering, measuring, optimizing and engaging across multiple operating systems, device and media. On September 20, 2018, Adobe reported an annual revenue of US\$9.03 billion. Operating income is US\$2.84billions and total assets are US\$18.76billions.

We have identified and analyzed alternative websites and discussed the possible information about the company and studying its business-level strategy including service strategy and new software development strategy. The paper also includes the company innovation on sustainability through a green strategy.

Keywords: Case Study, a Business strategy of IT company, ADOBE.

1. INTRODUCTION

Company analysis is an important type of case method in research methodology and is usually considered by the beginners of scholarly research. In today's Global market, providing quality products and services is essential for any manufacturer's continued growth, but maintaining a competitive edge is not always easy. For success quality awareness must begin at the conception of the product and continue throughout the various stages of its development. Adobe is an American multinational computer software company. Adobe Inc., formerly Adobe system Incorporated on May 9, 1997. The company is headquartered in San Jose, California, United States. Adobe is changing the world through digital experience. Adobe Founded in December 1982 by John Warnock and Charles Geschke. Who established the company after leaving Xerox PARC in order to develop and sell the Postscript were digital fonts, which they released in a proprietary format called Type 1. A systematic study and procedure are developed for company analysis and available for reference [1-10]. Many analysis frameworks are used in different company case studies to study the internal aspect of a company which includes ABCD analysis, SWOC analysis etc [11-19]. This paper involves

the study of the product and services of Adobe Company and its strategies to face competitions using various case study methodologies [20-26]. The internal and external opportunities analysis is done by means of SWOT analysis [17-19].

2. OBJECTIVES

- To understand the type of product and services provided by the company.
- To analyze the overall growth of the company.
- To find the competitors of ADOBE.
- To understand the corporate social responsibilities of the company.
- To find out the market share of the company.

3. ABOUT ADOBE COMPANY

The company was started in John Warnock Garage. The name of the company, ADOBE, comes from Adobe Creek in Los Altos, California, which ran behind Warnock's house. Adobe's corporate logo features a stylized "A" and was designed by Marva Warnock's wife. Warnock and Geschke considered various business options including a copy service business and a turnkey system for office printing. Adobe has historically focused upon the creation of multimedia and creativity software products, with a more recent foray towards digital marketing software. Adobe company chairman and CEO is Shantanu Narayen, and CFO is John F. Murphy and CTO is Abhay Parasnis. Adobe revenue in 2018 is US\$9.03 billion. Total asset is US\$18.76 billion. A microstock agency that presently provides over 57 million high-resolution, royalty-free image and video available to license. On December 11, 2014, Adobe announced it was buying Fotolia for \$800 million in cash, aiming at integrating the service to its creative cloud solution.

4. SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

Adobe offers various types of product and services.

Graphics design software: Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Page Maker, Adobe Light room, Adobe In Design, Adobe In Copy, Adobe Image Ready, Adobe Illustrators, Adobe Freehand, Adobe Frame Maker, Adobe Fireworks, Adobe Acrobat, Adobe XD.

Web design programs: Adobe Muse, Adobe Go Live, Adobe flash builder, Adobe Flash, Adobe Edge, Adobe Dream weaver, Adobe Contribute.

Video editing, animation, and visual effect: Adobe ultra, Adobe spark video, Adobe premiere pro, Adobe premiere Elements, Adobe prelude, Adobe Encore, Adobe Director, Adobe Animate, Adobe After Effect, Adobe Character Animator.

Audio editing software: Adobe Sound booth, Adobe Audition.

E-learning software: Adobe Captivate prime (LMS platform), Adobe Captivate, Adobe presenter video Express and Adobe connect (also a web conferencing platform).

Digital marketing management software: Adobe marketing cloud, Adobe Experience Manager (AEM 6.2), XML documentation add on (for AEM), MIXAMO.

Server platform: Adobe Cold Fusion, Adobe content server and Adobe Live Cycle Enterprise suite, Adobe Blaze Ds.

Format: Portable Document Format (PDF), PD F's predecessor PostScript, Action Script, shock wave Flash (SWF), Flash video (FLV), and filmstrip (.film).

Web-hosted service: Adobe color, Photo shop Express, Acrobat. Com, and Adobe spark.

Adobe consulting service: Tap into their full-service consultant who can help you to create

the right digital vision and customer experience to set your business apart.

Digital learning service: From on-site customized content to on-demand tutorials, learn how to establish a digital foundation, uncover insight and creates the right connections with customers. Get 24/7 help in multiple languages across the globe from your customer care team, documentation and community forum. Access their worldwide network of certified partners to solve your business's unique challenges and get the most out of adobe experience cloud.

Cloud services: Adobe creative cloud is a set of applications and services from Adobe system that gives subscribers access to a collection of software used for graphics design, Video editing, Web development, Photography, along with a set of mobile applications and also some optional cloud services.

5. ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

The escalating deterioration of the environment is a major concern for the business organization today. The green strategy implemented to improve the environmental sustainability and with supply chains evolving dynamically towards competitive advantage, Green supply chain management practice has gained importance in business research, Adobe company pleased to announce three new environmental sustainability goals.

- Archive Net Zero energy consumption by 2015 in their owned facilities in the United States.
- Reduce the amount of product packaging used per unit by 40 percent by 2012, and 80 percent by 2014.
- Expand their employee-led Green Team to all of their 12 major sites globally by 2015.

Adobe identified four steps for Adobe to achieve Net Zero around the world. 1.measure and manage energy usage. 2.reduce energy demand 3.Generate power on-site 4.Energy and carbon credit. The company believe their employees are agents of change, and they offer opportunities for them to contribute to and help craft our environmental sustainability initiatives. The green team facilitates an ongoing, company-wide discussion about environmental issues, and organizes educational programs and volunteer projects for fellow employees. Adobe employees empower its peers to make a difference and go beyond normal job descriptions to create a culture of sustainability within their company and the chair of the Green team represent the voice of employees as a member of the Adobe environmental sustainability council. Adobe's commitment to the Green Building movement has resulted in the certification of 10 LEED-platinum green building, approximately 45 percent of their worldwide square footage. In 3011, they began pursuing new LEED or LEED-equivalent certification for five adobe facilities outside of the United States, including their most recent certification in Beijing, chains and Noida, India.

6. HR TRAINING AND TRAINING STRATEGY

Adobe provides smooth and secure HR experiences to candidates and employees using adobe sign. Adobe sign is a critical part of effectively digitizing HR process throughout the employees' lifecycle. Adobe challenges the recruit top talent by delivering employment offers faster than the competition, reduce time and labor spent processing and human resource paperwork. provides new hires with a seamless recruiting and onboarding experience. A success of a company is not only a result of incredible manufacturing capability and great location. Developing a strategy for training gives your company a competitive advantage and helps propel you into the future. The plan needs to understand it so that everyone gets the

appropriate training at the right time.

7. FINANCIALS

Adobe achieved record quarterly revenue of \$2.29 billion in its third quarter of the fiscal year 2018, which represents 24 percent year-over-year revenue growth. Diluted earning per share was \$1.34 on a GAAP basis, and \$1.73 on a non-GAAP basis. Digital media segment revenue was \$1.61 billion, with creative revenue growing to \$1.36 billions and Document cloud achieving record revenue of \$249 million which represents 21 percent year-over-year growth. Operating income grew 32 percent and net income grew 59 percent year-over-year on a GAAP basis; operating income grew 32 percent and net income grew 57 percent year-over-year on a non-GAAP basis. Adobe repurchased approximately 2.9 millions of shares during the quarter, returning \$714 millions of cash to stockholders. Cash flow from operations was \$955 million, and deferred revenue grew 23 percent year-over-year to approximately \$2.71 billion.

8. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

The Adobe corporate social responsibility brief series share their current progress and continuing efforts to apply their creativity towards solving problems every day. Social responsibility is an ongoing journey with evolving expectations and challenges. They continuously explore new ways to integrate their strategies across business units, countries, and cultures; infuse CSR into Adobe employees' experience; and learn from a broad group of stockholders' perspectives. At Adobe, innovation doesn't apply only to the software they invest in; their employees and partner best ideas for solving social problems and creating positive change. Personal development meets professional development: they tie employees' pro bono projects and nonprofit board service to their professional development plans. So not only does their volunteer work strengthen their communities, but it advances their career as well. Good causes are their cause: The Adobe Foundation contributes millions in cash to help nonprofits run their operations, tell their stories and advance their missions. Investment that hits home: By partnering with employees to direct local investment of Adobe Foundation funds, we ensure that our support makes life better in our people's backyards. Teaming up for community action: When their employees join forces to create positive change, they're unstoppable. We support their efforts by giving them funds and opportunities to take action in their local communities.

9. ANALYSIS

Performance of the company:

The company went public in 1986, released the popular PDF document format in 1993. In 1996, Company headquarters were moved to San Jose, California. Over the years, Adobe released creative software developed in an internal team and acquired through mergers. Many of these are commonly recognized products like Photoshop, Acrobat Reader, and Creative Cloud. Today, The Company has offices in over 25 countries, employs over 18,000 employees, dominates the professional creative software market, and had revenue of over \$7.3 billion in 2017 alone.

Business Overview:

The company's digital media segment also includes its Document Cloud business, built around its Acrobat Reader and a set of integrated cloud-based document services. Customers also

include knowledge of workers. Who create, collaborate and distribute documents. Adobe Inc., develops, markets, and supports computer software product and technologies.

Strengths:

- Transition to subscription-based model.
- Strong market position in the digital media business.
- Strong global presence.
- Brand portfolio.
- Champion of the designer.
- Trustworthy and reliable.

Weakness:

- The company has not developed expertise in a Linux OS.
- Debt obligation.
- 360-degree feedback.
- Poor presence in the video animation market.
- Adobe has a wide range of products but many of them are not known to the public.

Opportunities:

- Acquisition of small companies, within the same market segment.
- Strong outlook for cloud computing.
- Partnership with Microsoft.
- The growth of the online market segment.
- With the growth of social media Facebook, Google + and others there is a growing market for photo and video editing hobbies.

Threats:

- Piracy.
- Open source software.
- Competition
- Security threats.

10. COMPETITORS**Oracle**

Oracle is perceived as one of Adobe's biggest rivals. Oracle was founded in 1977 in Redwood shores, California. Oracle is in the application software field. Oracle generate \$30.7B more revenue than adobe.

DocuSign

DocuSign is Adobe's #2 rival. DocuSign is a public company that was founded in 2003 in San Francisco, California. DocuSign competes in the internet software field. Compared to Adobe, DocuSign has 18969 fewer employees.

GIMP

GIMP is one of Adobe's top competitors. GIMP's headquarters is in Charlotte, North California, and was founded in 1996. Like Adobe, GIMP also operates 0.28% of Adobe's revenue.

11. SUGGESTION

Executive sponsorship is critical: Check-in needs to be role-modeled from the top.

Manager capabilities and development will break your success: we held numerous training session and staff meeting discussion to ensure understanding and adoption.

Communicate early and often: We engaged our employees in a dialogue before we made the move and regularly communicated progress.

Build a shared service model: our introduction of a employees resource center allowed the check-in process to scale effectively by providing adequate help and resources.

The product and service of Adobe technologies are analyzed as per the guidelines of case analysis methodology as given in standard company analysis methodology.

Keep your global lens: internationally there can be legal entities such as work council or cultural differences. Vet these concern early. Radically changing a long-held process such as performance reviews carries risk, and it is likely not the best choice for every company. But it has had a tremendous impact at adobe and encouraged us to look at others process through the same critical light, looking for opportunities to disrupt the status qua.

12. CONCLUSION:

Adobe still maintained the standard of products and services which they provide to the world. Adobe takes different steps for social and environmental development. The products and services of Adobe are analyzed as per the guidelines of case analysis methodology as given in standard company analysis methodology. The efforts of Adobe in maintaining the quality of its products and services are discussed and many possible improvements are suggested.

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